

You can securely generate a shared secret by communicating only on an insecure channel.

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Big ideas (core ideas, powerful ideas) are important ideas about a discipline that students should remember, even when technical details are lost. They are powerful and surprising ideas of the discipline (for a review see [Sba23, pp. 71-77]).

For instance, in cryptography, you can securely create a secret communicating only on an insecure channel (e.g., using the Diffie-Hellman-Merkle [DH06, Mer78] key exchange), a concept that revolutionizes security.

This is a very surprising fact and makes you marvel at the power of Informatics/CS/cryptography.

We have done several work on this [LSMa, LSM22, LMS23, LCM24, LSMb]

References

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